

WEAR RESISTANCE OF DLC COATED STEEL SUBSTRATES IN OIL LUBRICATION CONDITIONS FOR HYDRAULIC APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

The worldwide rotary pump market was estimated at around \$5000 million in 2020 and the market is supposed to increase by 20% toward the end of 2026, seeing a compounded annual growth rate of 3% over a period from 2022-2026. The scrapping of an engineered component made from non-renewable resources at an early stage in life due to wear goes against the ethics of the conservation of natural resources as the frictional processes lead to dissipation of a part of input energy. The objective of the this work was to obtain diamond-like carbon coating on high-speed steel samples and test them for better wear preventative behavior with different hydraulic fluids. The high-speed steel ball samples of 12.7 mm diameter were used as a substrate on which the diamond-like carbon coating was to be developed using the Radio-Frequency Plasma Enhanced Chemical Vapor Deposition (RF-PECVD) technique. The developed Diamond like Carbon coating was characterized by conducting X-Ray diffraction which suggested the coating to be of amorphous structure. In accordance with ASTM D4172, an investigation into the anti-wear characteristics of lubricating oil was carried out using the four-ball test. This test was carried out under certain conditions, including a higher load, a regulated temperature, and a constant rotational speed of the ball. The four ball results show that the coefficient of friction for samples reduces by around 36% when test oil 3 is used in uncoated samples and 48% in coated samples. Also, the wear rate for the test oil 3 for coated samples was found to be 0.7381×10^{-6} mm/Nm, which is the lowest wear rate among the other test oils. The outcome of the project is the reduction of coefficient of friction by 84% with respect to dry condition when test oil 3 is used. Hence, it can be concluded that test oil 3 is the best lubricant among the three test oils.

Keywords: High-Speed Steel Ball, Diamond Like Carbon Coating, Four Ball Test Wear Rate, Coefficient of Friction

1.0 Introduction

Because of factors such as mixing friction, sliding wear, corrosion, cavitation, and chemical impacts, a hydraulic vane pump with a fixed or variable displacement is subjected to a variety of wear when it is put through its paces over an extended period of time during normal operation; as a consequence, both its longevity and its effectiveness are diminished. Extensive research has been conducted on the wear that is brought on by the abrasion of tiny particles, especially in unlubricated systems. It has been discovered that the hardness of the surface that is being rubbed and the hardness, size, shape, and toughness of the abrasive particles are the most relevant characteristics. A significant amount of focus has also been directed toward abrasion in conjunction with lubricated systems. Ceramic coatings such as chromium oxide, aluminium oxide, titanium carbon nitride, or zirconium are utilised as wear coatings in a number of modern-day pump manufacturing companies. These coatings are

designed to extend the life of the pump. Because of the exceptional levels of corrosion resistance, hardness, thermal stability, and other characteristics that they possess. In addition to ceramic coatings, the diamond-like coating, also known as DLC, has gained acceptance. Diamond-like carbon (DLC) coatings are resilient enough to withstand the harshest wear conditions and high sliding speeds, even in the absence of any lubrication. This is because DLC coatings are extremely hard. Because they reduce the amount of frictional loss, engine components like fuel injection systems, valve trains, and pistons can benefit greatly from their use. The exceptional gliding qualities offered by DLC coatings are put to use in a wide variety of other applications as well. These applications include things like bearing shells and rollers, as well as textile machines and medical technologies. Pumps and compressors are also included in this category. Finding a suitable coating material with the needed attributes that are suitable for the base materials and suitable ways for coating the materials could be one of the solutions that could be implemented to reduce the amount of wear that takes place. Another solution that could be implemented to reduce the amount of wear that takes place would be to find a suitable way to reduce the amount of wear that takes place. Hydraulic fluids may also contain anti-wear compounds if the manufacturer so chooses to implement this option. Because vane pumps run at greater speeds for an extended period of time, the bonding strength is also a significant factor to take into consideration.

The current research study has been subjected to an analysis, and the results of this analysis are going to be reported in the section that comes after this one. Yangyi Xiao [1] et al. investigated the tribological behaviour of TiN, WC/C, and DLC coatings using the four-ball test, and found that among the three coatings studied, the TiN coating had the highest mean steady-state friction coefficient, while the DLC coating had the lowest. WC/C coatings were found to have the lowest mean steady-state friction coefficient. Rui Lan [2] et al. conducted research on the microstructural and wear characteristics of a DLC coating. The researchers used in-situ duplex plasma nitriding and arc ion plating as the processing methods for their study. They discovered that a-C: H coatings give enhanced wear resistance in basic PAO and also in fully formulated oils and fuels when contrasted to the uncoated steel surfaces. This was shown to be the case both in base PAO and in completely formulated oils and fuels. Karin Persson [3] and her colleagues investigated the effect that combining a DLC coating with water-based lubricants had on the coating's tribological behaviour. The DLC coated tribosystem exhibited a lower rate of wear based on the results of the tests. The DLC coating resulted in a considerable improvement across the board for all lubricants in terms of the resistance to seizing in the four-ball weld load. Xin He [4] et al., conducted research to determine the wear penalty caused by steel rubbing against hard coatings when using reactive lubricants. Tribochemical interactions are the source of this wear penalty. The steel ball lost a lot of material due to wear when it was pushed against the ceramic coating. More polar oil or a more reactive chemical considerably accelerated this wear loss. The wear behaviour of a hydrogenated DLC coating on a superelastic 60NiTi alloy for aviation self-lubricating spherical plain bearings was investigated by Yefei Zhou [5] et al. Because of their design, the bearings don't need to be oiled. This technique was used to deposit a layer of H-DLC onto the 60NiTi base material. It is clear from the results that the 60NiTi substrate has room for significant improvement in hardness, fracture

toughness, and plastic deformation resistance. Utilizing a textured-DLC coating to increase the wear resistance of stainless steel plate in a dusty lubricant environment is the focus of research conducted by Takuya Osawa et al. [6]. The study found that the wear resistance of surfaces with a DLC film and surface texturing was higher than that of an untreated stainless steel substrate, and the specific wear rate in dusty settings was about 1/20.

Researchers Luciane Yumi Suzuki de Oli [7] et al., investigated the wear behaviour of DLC deposited on titanium dioxide and titanium dioxide that had been treated with surface mechanical attrition. It is common knowledge that diamond-like carbon coatings can increase the wear resistance of surfaces that are subjected to continual friction. Because of their weak adhesion to the substrate, such coatings are often incompatible with the use of surgical components. Ervin Strmcnik [8] et al., investigated the effect that a mechanical component with a DLC coating had on the functioning of an orbital hydraulic motor while it was submerged in water. The discs saw very little wear and tear, which in some cases was so minimal that it was practically impossible to measure. According to the wear coefficient and the results of the surface study, the worn surfaces included almost no faults. This was consistent with the determined wear coefficient. Ming-xue Shen [9] et al., investigated the fretting wear properties of acrylonitrile-butadiene rubber (NBR). Compared to DLC and graphene coatings, this procedure was carried out. Experimental results revealed that the fretting running regime for graphene coating was significantly different from that of DLC coating and steel substrate. Luca Nobili [10] and others collaborated on the development of DLC coatings for hydraulic applications. Depending on the characteristics of the substrate, the morphological and chemical studies of the wear tracks show that the failure of the coating could have been caused by either abrasive wear or delamination. R. Sola [11] et al., investigated PVD coatings for reducing friction and wear in swash plate axial piston pumps and motors. Microstructural examinations have revealed that all of the samples include a coating that is homogenous, relatively thin, and firmly attached to the substrate.

From the literature survey it is noticed that the Wear Resistance of DLC coated steel substrates in oil lubrication conditions for hydraulic applications has not been attempted so far. Hence the present research is focused on to coat diamond-like carbon on a HSS M2 cylindrical pin, with the suitable deposition method based on the commercial availability and viability. To characterize the surface of both the bare substrate and the coated material using the appropriate techniques. To evaluate of coefficient of friction and wear scar using pin on disc tribometer, To conduct wear characterization post wear testing of the specimen, for identification of wear tracks, and subsequently evaluate their nature.

Hence the goal of the current research is to study the wear performance of DLC coated HSS steel substrate with different lubricated hydraulic oils such as ISO VG32, ISO VG46 and ISO VG68.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 HSS Balls

2.1.1 Specifications of HSS Balls

- Weight Of Ball : **8.8 gm**
- Diameter Of Ball : **12.7 mm**
- Hardness : **415 HV**
- Average Roughness : **0.93 μm**

2.2 Diamond like Carbon (A-C: H)

2.2.1 Properties of Diamond like Carbon (A-C: H)

- Extremely hard
- Low friction losses
- Ideal for high speeds
- Excellent abrasion protection
- Higher sliding velocity

2.2.2 Specifications of DLC Coated HSS Balls

- Coating Material: **Diamond Like Carbon (a-C:H)**
- Coating Technology: **PECVD**
- Weight of Ball: **8.97 gm**
- Coating Thickness: **3 μm**
- Hardness: **~1500-2500 HV**

2.2.3 Coating Architecture Used-a-C: H Coating Architecture:

Standard sputtering techniques permit graphite targets to synthesise the hydrogenated a-C: H surface layer. However, this process must be reactive in order to form a layer with the desired hardness. Sputtered a-C: H typically has a hardness value that is significantly higher than a-C: H made using PECVD. However, as the coating would be too soft otherwise, reactive sputtering is required. The performance in terms of friction might arc toward ta-C for high-volume production. Although the delayed application method makes the coating more expensive, it is nonetheless used in high-volume manufacturing due to the coating's superior friction performance. Figure 1 (a) and (b) shows HSS Balls before and after DLC coating.

Fig: 1 (a) HSS Balls

Fig: 1 (b) DLC Coated HSS Balls

2.3 Selection of Oil

One of the most crucial parts of a hydraulic system is hydraulic fluid. It carries out a variety of tasks, including power transmission, lubrication, heat transfer, and the transportation of contaminants, wear debris, and sludge. Given the significant roles that fluids play, choosing the right fluid is essential for maximizing the performance and lifespan of hydraulic pumps, motors, and other components.

2.3.1 Typical Properties of oil

Table 1: Typical Properties of Lubricant Oil

Naming Convention	Test Oil 1	Test Oil 2	Test Oil 3
Aw Hydraulic Grade	32	46	68
Iso Viscosity Grade	32	46	68
Density@ 15°C,kg/m ³	854	857	865
Pour Point °C	-39	-36	-33
Flash Point °C	230	248	254
Viscosity Index	115	114	111
Rust Test	Pass	Pass	Pass
Denison HF- Pump Test	Approved	Approved	Approved
Oxidation Stability,hrs D-943	5000+	5000+	5000+
33VQ25 Vane Pump Test	Pass	Pass	Pass

Table 1 shows the different important properties of the oil like ISO Grade, Density, Viscosity and test results that were taken into consideration for selection of oils. The test oils 032, 046 and 068 is shown in the below Figure 2.

Fig: 2: Test oil 1, 2 and 3.

2.4 Four-Ball Wear Test Machine

In order to evaluate the anti-wear capabilities of lubricating oil under a variety of conditions, like higher load, regulated temperature, and continuous rotating speed of the ball, a four-ball tester is utilised.

Standard Used

American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM D4172)

Temperature: 75 degree celsius

Speed : 1200 rotations per minute

Duration : 60 minutes

Load : 392 Newtons

2.4.1 Experimental Procedure

The tests are performed in line with the standard test techniques for the determination of wear preventative qualities of Lubricating Fluids, utilising a standard known as ASTM D4172. Each new round of testing uses balls that have recently been coated with carbon that resembles diamond. As shown in Figures 3 (a), 3 (b), and 3 (c), the coated steel balls are inserted in the oil cup system, and the oil cup is then tightened with a torque wrench to prevent the coated steel balls at the bottom of the oil cup from moving throughout the tests (c). The faster-spinning ball is inserted into the collet, and the collet is then tightened onto the spindle. The oil cup system is then prepared for the addition of the test lubricant. It is imperative that the oil completely fills the test cup arrangement in its entirety before proceeding.

Fig: 3 (a) Arrangement of balls in experiment Fig: 3 (b) four ball testing conduction

Fig: 3 (c) Four Ball Tester

In order to prevent shock, the test load of 392 newtons is gradually given to the upper ball of the four-ball machine after the components of the oil cup assembly have been fitted into the frictionless disc of the four-ball machine. After that, the lubricant is brought up to the appropriate temperature of 75 degrees Celsius by heating it. As soon as the target temperature is reached, the drive motor is programmed to start rotating the top ball at a rate of 1200 times per minute. After the one-hour duration of the test, the heater was turned off and the oil cup system was removed from the machine. Following the removal of the test oil, a tissue is utilised to clean the area surrounding the scar. The bottom balls are then positioned on a base for the microscope that is intended to securely hold the balls during the process of microscopic analysis. Under a microscope, assessments of the wear spot are taken on each of the three bottom balls, and these results are then compared.

3.0 Results and Discussions

3.1 X Ray Diffraction

A crystal is made up of atoms that are organized in a specific pattern across all three dimensions of space. Amorphous materials, on the other hand, lack this uniformity, and their atoms are dispersed randomly throughout three-dimensional space. As a result, this serves as the

foundation for distinguishing between an amorphous structure and a crystalline structure in the coating. When X-rays impact atom-formed lattice planes in a periodic arrangement of atoms, they scatter in only specific directions. This occurs when atoms are arranged in a periodic fashion. Because of this, there is a possibility that high intensity peaks will result, with the width of the peaks being proportionally smaller than their height. Whereas in case of an amorphous structure the X-rays are scattered in many directions resulting in an oversized bump distributed during a wide selection (two Theta) rather than high intensity narrower peaks. As shown in Figure 4 no sharp peaks are observed in the intensity v/s two theta graph concluding amorphous structure of the coating.

Fig: 4 X Ray Diffraction Graph Intensity v/s two theta

3.2 Four Ball Test

Table 2: Four ball test results

Sample ID	Type	Scar diameter in mm			
		Ball 1	Ball 2	Ball 3	Average
Test oil 1	Uncoated	0.628	0.615	0.62	0.621
	Coated	0.558	0.571	0.568	0.565
Test oil 2	Uncoated	0.593	0.591	0.584	0.589
	Coated	0.538	0.533	0.529	0.533
Test oil 3	Uncoated	0.602	0.561	0.569	0.577
	Coated	0.48	0.471	0.476	0.475

There are a total of six experimental setups that are performed using four ball tribometers which include three tests using the uncoated ball samples and three coated ball samples and each test done with one oil sample at a time. As per the result as shown in Table 2 it is observed that for all the oil samples the wear scar diameter obtained has reduced effectively for the coated ball sample as compared to uncoated. Observing the differences of the average wear scar diameter for each oil sample it is clearly observed that oil sample test oil 3 reduces the wear scar diameter most effectively in comparison with test oil 2 and test oil 1. Figures 5 (a), 5 (b), 5 (c), 5 (d), 5 (e), 5 (f) shows wear scar images of the tested balls generated by optical microscopy.

Fig: 5 (a) Wear scar for uncoated - test oil 3 samples

Fig: 5 (b) Wear scar for coated - test oil 3 sample

Fig: 5 (c) Wear scar for uncoated - test oil 2 sample

Fig: 5 (d) Wear scar for coated - test oil 2 sample

Fig: 5 (e) Wear scar for uncoated - test oil 1 sample

Fig: 5 (f) Wear scar for coated - test oil 1 sample

This explains that oil sample 3 displays the nature of slowest wear rate in the four-ball test and hence is successfully able to display good wear preventive behavior. This nature of slow wear rate of test oil 3 as compared to other samples occurs as it provides higher shearing stability which means that during the life cycle the viscosity loss is the least than in the cases of test oil 2 and test oil 1.

Fig: 6 Comparison of wear scar diameter for different lubricants

More the scar diameter, the more the wear. The graph in Figure 6 shows that wear is minimum when test oil 3 oil is used as compared to other lubricants. Moreover, DLC coating shows further reduction in wear as compared to uncoated condition.

Another metric, known as the wear rate, can also be utilised to assess the degree of wear. The tests are carried out over the course of one hour at a steady rotating speed of 1200 revolutions

per minute. Deleanu, L. estimated the sliding distances for one hour as follows: L1200 = 1641.6 metres ($v = 0.456$ metres per second or revolutions per minute). As a result of the differences in sliding distances, it is quite likely that the graph illustrating the WSD's reliance on the test parameter is nonsensical; hence, the wear can also be assessed by another parameter which is known as the wear rate, which is based on the research that has been done in this area.

$$W = \text{WSD} / F \cdot L$$

Where, W=Wear Rate in mm/N.m

WSD = Average Wear scar diameter for a test,

F= Load applied on the four balls,

L= the sliding distance.

In other terms, the wear rate is the mass or volume loss of the material per unit of mechanical work performed by the system. The product F-L represents the amount of mechanical work accomplished by the tribosystem.

Fig: 7 Comparison of wear rate for different lubricants

The graph in Figure 7 shows that wear is minimum when test oil 3 oil is used as compared to other lubricants. Moreover, DLC coating shows further reduction in wear as compared to uncoated condition.

Fig: 8 Coefficient of friction for uncoated samples

Fig: 9 Coefficient of friction for coated samples

Figure 8 shows the coefficient of friction for uncoated samples during the one hour of four ball wear testing. Figure 9 shows the same for coated samples. The coefficient of friction increases as the test starts and gets fairly constant after sometime. For both the conditions, coated and uncoated the coefficient of friction is least of test oil 3 oil. The high viscosity of test oil 3 helps in reducing this value as compared to other two lubricants. The coefficient of friction values for test oil 1 and test oil 2 are almost similar and thus, do not show much difference. When comparing the two graphs, an overall decrease in coefficient of friction is evident in the case of coated samples. This shows that the DLC coating has helped in reducing the coefficient of friction.

Table 3: Average Coefficient of Friction of different samples

Oil	Average Coefficient of Friction	
	Uncoated Samples	Coated Samples
Test oil 1	0.0667	0.0619
Test oil 2	0.0718	0.0601
Test oil 3	0.0438	0.0316

Table 3 shows average coefficient of friction of different samples. A significant reduction in coefficient of friction by around 48% is observed for the test oil 3 in coated samples and 36% for uncoated samples. The high viscosity of test oil 3 helps in reducing this value as compared to other two lubricants. This makes this lubricant better than the other two in terms of reducing friction. Also, coating the samples with DLC has helped in further reducing the coefficient of friction by 28% for test oil 3, making it suitable for the required applications.

4. Conclusion

The following conclusions are made from the characterization tests of DLC coatings and wear test of DLC coated high speed steel with hydraulic oils.

- DLC Coating of thickness 3 μm was successfully deposited at Oerlikon Balzers facility on HSS Ball substrate, procured from Ducom Instruments using RF-PECVD technique.
- From the XRD study it is noted that no sharp peaks are observed in the intensity v/s two theta graph concluding amorphous structure of the coating.
- The wear performance of DLC coated HSS steel balls under different lubricated hydraulic oils such as ISO VG32, ISO VG46, and ISO VG68 were successfully evaluated using the four-ball method.
- From the four ball test it was deduced that oil sample test oil 3 with viscosity 68 shows the best wear preventative properties as compared to other oil samples as it was able to bring the wear scar diameter to the lower range when DLC coating was applied to that of uncoated.

References

- [1] Yangyi Xiao, Wankai Shin, Jing Luo, Yijian Liao (2014), The tribological performance of TiN, WC/C and DLC coatings measured by the four-ball test, *Ceramics International* 40, 6919-6925.
- [2] Rui Lana, Zhifeng Maa, Chunji Wang, Guoying Lub, Yanyan Yuana, Changlun Shib (2019), Microstructural and tribological characterization of DLC coating by in-situ duplex plasma nitriding and arc ion plating, *Diamond & Related Materials*, 98,107473, 1-6.
- [3] Karin Persson, Rickard Gahlin (2003), Tribological performance of a DLC coating in combination with water-based lubricants, *Tribology International*, 36, 851-855.
- [4] Xin He, Harry M. Meyer, Huimin Luo, and Jun Qu (2015), Wear Penalty for Steel Rubbing Against Hard Coatings in Reactive Lubricants due to Tribochemical interactions, 1-24.

- [5] Yefei ZHOU, Zhihao Chen, Zhonghui HU, Lei LI, Qingxiang Yang, Xiaolei XinG, (2021), Tribological performance of hydrogenated diamond-like carbon coating deposited on superelastic 60NiTi alloy for aviation self-lubricating spherical plain bearings, Chinese Journal of Aeronautics, 1-12.
- [6] Takuya Osawa, Makoto Matsuo, Yuya Eyama, Hiroshi Yamamoto (2020), Using Textured-DLC Coating to Improve the Wear Resistance of Stainless Steel Plate Under Dust-Containing Lubricant Condition, Int. J. of Automation Technology, Vol.14 No.1, 99-108.
- [7] Luciane Yumi Suzuki de Oliveiraa, Carlos José Mesquita Siqueirab, Beatriz Luci Fernandesa (2019), Wear behavior of Diamond-like Carbon Deposited on Ti6Al4V Prepared with Surface Mechanical Attrition Treatment, Materials Research; 22(2): e20180568,1-5.
- [8] Ervin Strmcnik , Franc Majdic and Mitjan Kalin (2019), Influence of a Diamond-Like Carbon-Coated Mechanical Part on the Operation of an Orbital Hydraulic Motor in Water, Metals, 9, 466; doi:10.3390/met9040466, 1-14.
- [9] Ming-xue Shen, Feng Dong, Yi Ma, Jin-fang Peng, Min-Hao Zhu (2017), Fretting wear behaviors of acrylonitrile-butadiene rubber (NBR) against diamond-like carbon and graphene coatings, Int J Adv Manuf Technol, 1-11, DOI 10.1007/s00170-017-0946-1,.
- [10] Luca Nobili, Luca Magagnin (2019), DLC coatings for hydraulic applications, Transactions of Nonferrous Metals Society of China, 19, 810-813.
- [11] R. Sola, P. Veronesi, B. Zardin, M. Borghi (2020), A study on PVD coatings for reduction of friction and wear of swash plate axial piston pumps and motors, International Journal of the Italian Association for Metallurgy, 14-23.